

Treatment Patterns, Medication Adherence, and Drug Resistance among Tuberculosis Patients in South India: A Cross-Sectional Study

Balamurugan K^{1*}, Manikandan.S¹, Shankarananth V²

^{1*} *Department of Pharmacy, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram, Tamil Nadu, India-608002.*

¹ *S.A. Raja Pharmacy College, Vadakkankulam, Tirunelveli District, Tamil Nadu, India -627116.*

² *S.A. Raja Pharmacy College, Vadakkankulam, Tirunelveli District, Tamil Nadu, India -627116.*

Abstracts

Background: Tuberculosis (TB) remains a leading public health concern globally, with India accounting for 27% of all reported cases. The emergence and rising prevalence of drug-resistant TB (DR-TB), particularly multidrug-resistant (MDR) and rifampicin-resistant (RR) strains, threaten TB elimination efforts, especially in high-burden regions like Tamil Nadu.

Methods: This cross-sectional study, conducted between November 2022 and April 2024, assessed treatment patterns, medication adherence, and drug resistance among 215 TB patients attending DOTS centers in Tamil Nadu. Sociodemographic and clinical data were collected, and drug resistance profiles were analyzed. Medication adherence was evaluated using the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale-8. Statistical associations were explored using chi-square and logistic regression analyses.

Results: Males constituted 70.3% of cases, with the majority from rural and lower socioeconomic backgrounds. Pulmonary TB was predominant (78.1%), but MDR-TB was alarmingly high (43.7%), and adherence rates were suboptimal, especially among recurrent, HIV-positive, or low-education patients. Second-line TB drugs were prescribed more frequently for retreatment or MDR-TB cases. Factors such as poor adherence, low education, HIV co-infection, and previous treatment were linked to resistance.

Conclusions: The high burden of drug resistance and poor adherence highlight urgent needs for targeted interventions, enhanced counseling, and adherence-focused programs. Addressing both individual and systemic barriers will be critical to reducing relapse and advancing progress toward TB elimination in India.

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), tuberculosis (TB) remains a significant global health threat. In 2021, approximately 10.6 million TB cases were reported, affecting individuals across all age groups and regions. TB is currently the second leading cause of death worldwide after COVID-19, with 1.3 million deaths recorded in 2022 (*TB incidence. WHO. 2023.*)

India accounted for 27% of global TB cases in 2022, the highest incidence worldwide (*TB incidence. WHO. 2023.*) This statistic highlights the urgent need for comprehensive TB control measures and sufficient resources to address this significant public health issue (*TB incidence. WHO. 2023; WHO Global TB Report 2022*) The National TB Elimination Programme of India responded to COVID-19-related disruptions by implementing mandatory reporting, door-to-door case detection campaigns, and expanding diagnostic capabilities. Consequently, reported TB cases in 2021 surpassed 2.14 million, an 18% increase from the previous year. These outcomes reflect India's proactive strategies in TB identification and treatment, contributing to a decline in incidence rates and improved community health (*TB incidence. WHO. 2023; WHO Global TB Report 2022; Global TB Report 2022.*)

Multidrug-resistant and rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis (MDR/RR-TB) are strains resistant to most first-line anti-tubercular drugs. Treatment of MDR/RR-TB is more complex and costly than drug-susceptible TB. In 2022, the WHO reported approximately 558,000 new MDR/RR-TB cases globally, resulting in an estimated 160,000 deaths. Despite a slight decline in MDR/RR-TB cases since 2015, it remains a significant public health concern, prompting the WHO to prioritize it in global TB control initiatives (*Drug-resistant TB. 2023*). Despite a modest decline in TB cases from 2015 to 2021, recent data indicate an increase in TB incidence, reversing previous downward trends. The emergence of drug-resistant TB strains, often resulting from antimicrobial misuse, further complicates epidemic control. Global TB-related mortality increased from 2019 to 2021, largely due to healthcare disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (*Bai W, 2024; Cilloni L, 2020*)

Globally, TB remains a threat due to new strains of the disease that are drug-resistant and multidrug-resistant. The elimination of tuberculosis by 2050 is feasible if better drugs,

diagnostics, and vaccines are developed to detect and treat active infections and latent TB as well. MDR TB (including rifampicin resistance) can be detected at the population level with rapid and highly sensitive diagnostic tools (Gene-Xpert, TB-Quick). TB has been associated with several molecular mechanisms, including vitamin D's protective effect. Epigenetic mechanisms (histone binding) impair the immune response to this pathogen. Precision diagnostics with AI are like a scalpel, providing privacy and collaboration whilst providing precision diagnosis without causing too much damage. The result of AI must include decades of knowledge gleaned from imaging, clinical, and bacterial data, as well as epidemiological and bacterial data, to maximise the technology's impact. (*Merchant SA, 2022*)

India is the major contributing country to new TB cases in the world. TB stands as the third leading cause of mortality among all communicable diseases in India, with a significant proportion of cases with resistance to the commonly used drug, Rifampicin. In 2022, the WHO reported a total of 58,837 cases of MDR or RR TB, with 10,935 cases classified as pre-XDR XDR TB. The prevalence and incidence rates of MDR/RR-TB in India are 316 and 8.5 per 100,000 population, respectively. (*Vishwakarma D, 2023*)

With this, the present study aimed to comprehensively assess treatment patterns, medication adherence, and the burden and predictors of drug resistance among tuberculosis patients attending DOTS centers in Tamil Nadu, India, and to identify factors associated with poor adherence and drug-resistant TB.

METHODOLOGY:

Study Design

This is a cross sectional study to comprehensively assess treatment patterns, drug resistance, and medication adherence among TB patients. The study was conducted between November 2022 and April 2024 among TB patients registered at selected Directly Observed Treatment, Short-course (DOTS) centers across both urban and rural settings, across Tamil Nadu state, India.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Patients of all ages and with any co-morbid conditions diagnosed with tuberculosis and undergoing treatment according to the Revised National Tuberculosis Control Program (RNTCP)

guidelines were included in the study. This encompassed both newly diagnosed and previously treated patients, who had been on anti-TB treatment for at least two months. Patients who were severely ill or unwilling to provide consent were excluded from participation. Additionally, pregnant and lactating women, as well as individuals diagnosed with mental illnesses, were excluded to ensure the consistency and reliability of the dataset.

Ethical Considerations

Confidentiality of patient data was prioritized throughout the study. All collected data were anonymized before analysis to ensure privacy and compliance with ethical standards. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of the host institution, and permissions were granted by relevant TB control authorities. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants after explaining the study's objectives, benefits, and potential risks.

Sample size and Data Collection

Sample size was determined using Cochran's formula for cross-sectional studies, assuming an anticipated non-adherence rate of 30%, 95% confidence interval, and 5% precision, with an additional 10% to compensate for non-response.

Data were collected using a pre-structured form and subsequently recorded in an Excel spreadsheet for analysis. The form captured key variables, including sociodemographic information, treatment history, medication adherence (assessed using the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale-8). Clinical and laboratory data such as treatment regimen, sputum results, culture findings, and drug susceptibility test (DST) results were extracted from TB registers and patient records. Drug details, including names, dosages, treatment durations, and prescribing physicians, were also documented.

The classification of TB cases was based on patients' history of treatment and drug resistance profiles. New cases were defined as those who had not undergone prior TB treatment or had received anti-TB drugs for less than one month. Previously treated cases were further subclassified into recurrent cases (previously treated and microbiologically confirmed positive for

TB), treatment failures (patients whose previous treatment failed), those treated after loss to follow-up, and other cases with undocumented or unknown outcomes.

Drug resistance patterns were categorized into mono-resistance (resistance to one first-line drug), poly-drug resistance (resistance to multiple first-line drugs excluding both isoniazid and rifampicin), multi-drug resistance (resistance to both isoniazid and rifampicin), rifampicin resistance (resistance to rifampicin with or without resistance to other drugs), and extensively drug-resistant TB (MDR-TB with additional resistance to at least one fluoroquinolone and one second-line injectable agent).

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS software version 20. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, means, and percentages, were calculated to summarize socio-demographic and clinical parameters. Chi-square tests were employed for categorical variables to explore associations between socio-demographic factors, adherence patterns, and clinical characteristics such as site of infection and drug resistance profiles. Additionally, univariate analysis was performed to identify significant relationships. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

This structured methodology provides a comprehensive framework for analyzing treatment adherence, drug resistance patterns, and clinical outcomes in TB management within the study population.

RESULTS

The socio-demographic and behavioral characteristics of the 215 tuberculosis (TB) patients included in the study are summarized in Table 1. Among the participants, a significant majority were male (70.3%), while females constituted 29.7% ($p=0.03$). The age distribution revealed the largest proportion of cases in the 41-50 age group (29.6%), followed by 31-40 years (21.8%), and 18-30 years (15.6%). Patients aged <18 years accounted for only 4.6%, and those over 60 years represented 11% of the cohort ($p=0.05$).

The majority of TB patients resided in rural areas (64%), compared to 36% in urban areas ($p=0.01$). Socioeconomic status (SES) analysis showed that 64% of patients belonged to the lower class, while 28.1% were from the middle class, and only 7.8% were from the upper class; this distribution was not statistically significant ($p=0.12$). Majority of the patients were low educated (40%). Behavioral risk factors were prevalent among the patients, with smoking being the most common (71.8%, $p=0.02$), followed by alcohol consumption (57.8%, $p=0.09$). Illicit drug use was reported by 12.5% of participants but was not significantly associated with TB occurrence ($p=0.15$).

Table 2 details the clinical characteristics of tuberculosis (TB) patients admitted to the tertiary care hospital. Among the 215 patients, new TB cases comprised 29.6%, while recurrent TB cases were more prevalent at 36%. Cases requiring treatment after failure and treatment after loss to follow-up were 15.6% and 14%, respectively. A smaller proportion (4.6%) were classified as other previously treated patients ($p=0.03$) (Figure 1).

Pulmonary TB was the main infection site, comprising 78.1% of cases, with extrapulmonary TB at 21.8% ($p=0.01$). Multidrug-resistant TB (MDR) was found in 43.7%, while rifampicin resistance (RR) and mono-resistance (MR) were each 7.8%. Extensively drug-resistant TB (XRD) was rare at 1.5%. Susceptible strains were present in 34.3% ($p=0.05$). A family history of TB was noted in 25% of cases ($p=0.08$), and HIV co-infection was present in 34.3% ($p=0.01$). Other comorbidities occurred in 29.6% ($p=0.09$). Nearly half (48.4%) had prior first-line treatment, and 11% had second-line treatment. Surgical interventions for TB were done in 18.8% ($p=0.15$) (Table 2).

Figure 3 presents the anti-tubercular regimens employed for treating new and retreatment TB cases. Among all cases ($N=215$), the most frequently used regimens included combinations of fluoroquinolones with other drugs (81.2%) and second-line injectables with other drugs (76.5%). Regimens combining both first-line and second-line drugs were used in 39% of cases.

In new TB cases ($N=54$), fluoroquinolone-based regimens were used in 10.9% of cases, while second-line injectables with other drugs were prescribed in 12.5%. Regimens such as HRZES (3.1%) and HRE/HRZ/HZE/RZE (3.1%) were limited to specific indications.

Table 3 outlines the factors associated with the use of second-line anti-tubercular drugs among the 215 TB patients in the study. Male patients (54.6%) were more likely to be prescribed second-line TB drugs compared to females (15.6%), with an odds ratio (OR) of 2.1 (95% CI: 0.28–3.2). Age-specific trends indicated that patients aged 41-50 years had the highest odds (OR: 2.15, 95% CI: 1.23–3.6), followed by those aged 31-40 years (OR: 1.81, 95% CI: 1.20–3.0). Interestingly, the likelihood of second-line drug use was lower in the elderly (>60 years; OR: 0.31, 95% CI: 0.02–1.3). Retreatment cases (59.3%) had a significantly higher association with second-line drug prescription compared to new TB cases (4.6%), with an OR of 3.1 (95% CI: 1.62–4.21). Patients with pulmonary TB were more likely to receive second-line drugs (48.4%) than those with extrapulmonary TB (21.8%), although this association was not statistically significant (OR: 1.6, 95% CI: 0.5–2.41).

Drug resistance patterns demonstrated the strongest association with second-line drug use. Multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) cases had the highest odds (OR: 2.71, 95% CI: 1.62–3.89) for second-line drug prescriptions. Patients with rifampicin resistance, mono-resistance, poly-drug resistance, and extensively drug-resistant TB showed lower and non-significant associations.

The distribution of anti-tubercular drug prescriptions in new versus recurrent TB cases reveals important differences in drug use. Isoniazid (29.7% new vs. 31.25% recurrent) and rifampicin (25% new vs. 29.7% recurrent) were commonly prescribed across both groups. However, pyrazinamide (29.7% vs. 51.6%) and ethambutol (31.25% vs. 59.4%) were utilized significantly more in recurrent cases, indicating a reliance on these drugs for treatment failures or resistance. Streptomycin saw a notable increase in recurrent cases (26.6% vs. 3.1% in new cases) to address drug-resistant strains. Among fluoroquinolones, levofloxacin was notably higher in recurrent cases (48.4% vs. 4.7% in new cases). Second-line drugs, including rifaximin (17.2%), linezolid (25%), and amikacin (14.1%) were primarily used in recurrent cases, underscoring their importance for multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB). Other supportive agents like pyridoxine (45.3%) and amoxicillin/clavulanate (40.6%) were more prevalent in retreatment scenarios. Less common drugs, such as ethionamide and PAS, were primarily found in recurrent cases, highlighting their critical roles in complex regimens (Figure 4).

Table 4 summarizes medication adherence among tuberculosis patients was assessed using the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8). Among newly diagnosed TB patients, 60.9%

demonstrated high adherence, compared to only 36.4% among recurrent cases. Conversely, low adherence was substantially higher among recurrent TB patients (29.8%) than among new cases (10.9%). The mean adherence score was 7.1 ± 1.4 for new TB cases and 6.2 ± 3.2 for recurrent cases, and this difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.003$). The overall Chi-square test confirmed a significant association between treatment category and adherence level ($p = 0.002$). These findings suggest that recurrent TB patients are more likely to experience challenges with medication adherence

Multivariable logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent predictors of medication non-adherence among tuberculosis patients (Table 5). After adjusting for potential confounders, several variables showed significant associations with non-adherence. Patients with a low level of education (\leq primary) were twice as likely to be non-adherent compared with those with higher education levels (AOR = 2.11; 95% CI: 1.09–4.07; $p = 0.027$). Similarly, individuals diagnosed with MDR-TB had nearly twice the odds of non-adherence relative to HIV-negative patients (AOR = 2.54; 95% CI: 1.33–4.82; $p = 0.005$). Moreover, patients diagnosed with HIV were three times more likely to exhibit poor adherence compared to those with drug-sensitive TB (AOR = 3.06; 95% CI: 1.11–8.44; $p = 0.034$).

DISCUSSION

The study revealed a predominance of male TB patients (70.3%), consistent with Indian studies linking male vulnerability to higher exposure to risk factors like smoking, alcohol use, and occupational hazards. Social stigma and healthcare barriers likely contribute to underreporting among females. TB incidence peaked in the 41–50 age group, aligning with RNTCP data that highlights vulnerability in productive age groups due to occupational risks and comorbidities like diabetes. Rural areas accounted for 64% of cases, reflecting national trends tied to poor living conditions and limited healthcare access, underscoring the need for rural-specific interventions.

This study highlights critical challenges in tuberculosis (TB) management in South India, emphasizing the high burden of recurrent TB (36%), often linked to suboptimal treatment and poor adherence (Sharma et al., 2019). Treatment failures (15.6%) and loss to follow-up (14%) underline the need for improved patient tracking systems (Chadha et al., 2020).

Pulmonary TB (78.1%) predominates, but extrapulmonary TB (21.8%) poses diagnostic challenges, contributing to significant morbidity (Tiwari et al., 2018). Alarming, multidrug-

resistant TB (43.7%) exceeds national averages, with rifampicin resistance (7.8%) and XDR-TB (1.5%) further complicating management. Poor adherence and inadequate treatment are key drivers of resistance (**Jain et al., 2021**).

HIV co-infection (34.3%) and other comorbidities (29.6%) significantly affect outcomes, demanding integrated care (**Nair et al., 2018**). First-line drug failure (48.4%) stresses the need for stringent initial treatment protocols. Tailored interventions, improved surveillance, and patient-centric adherence programs are essential for advancing TB control in the region.

The use of standard first-line regimens such as HRZES and HRE/HRZ/HZE/RZE (each 3.1%) in new TB cases aligns with global guidelines for drug-susceptible TB. However, the low usage of these regimens indicates a growing prevalence of primary drug resistance, underscoring the need for drug susceptibility testing at diagnosis. Similar findings by Kant et al. (2019) emphasize the increasing incidence of primary drug resistance in India, necessitating early detection and tailored treatment.

In retreatment cases, the predominance of fluoroquinolone-based regimens (70.3%) and second-line injectable drugs (67.18%) highlights the significant burden of multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) in South India. These trends mirror national challenges, where MDR-TB is a predominant concern in retreatment scenarios (**Gopalan et al., 2021**). The observed reliance on second-line regimens without first-line agents in 9.3% of cases underscores the alarming progression toward extensively drug-resistant TB (XDR-TB).

The use of individualized regimens combining first-line and second-line drugs (39%) reflects the shift from standardized to resistance-tailored treatments. While this enhances therapeutic efficacy, it places a significant demand on healthcare systems for proper monitoring and adherence management. **Desikan et al. (2020)** emphasize the critical role of molecular diagnostics in guiding regimen selection, minimizing adverse effects, and improving overall outcomes. These findings highlight the urgent need for enhanced diagnostic tools and adherence strategies to address the complexities of TB treatment.

The substantial proportion of retreatment cases requiring advanced regimens, such as fluoroquinolones and second-line injectables, underscores significant gaps in initial treatment adherence and follow-up. Socioeconomic barriers, limited patient education, and incomplete treatment courses are key factors driving this trend (**Chakraborty et al., 2018**). These challenges highlight the urgent need for targeted strategies to ensure treatment completion and reduce the

reliance on complex regimens that are resource-intensive and often associated with poorer outcomes.

The study highlights significant gender and age associations with the prescription of second-line TB drugs. Males were more likely to receive second-line regimens, consistent with national data linking higher TB burden and resistance trends in men to behavioral risk factors like smoking and alcohol use (**Bhargava et al., 2013**). Middle-aged individuals (41–50 years) exhibited increased odds of second-line drug use due to greater occupational and environmental exposures, whereas older patients (>60 years) had lower odds, possibly reflecting the challenges of tolerating aggressive regimens (**Chakraborty et al., 2018**).

Retreatment cases demonstrated a significantly higher likelihood of requiring second-line drugs (OR: 3.1), highlighting persistent challenges such as incomplete treatment and poor adherence (**Chadha et al., 2020**). Pulmonary TB cases were more strongly associated with second-line drug use compared to extrapulmonary TB, likely due to its higher bacterial load and prioritization in diagnostic protocols (**Tiwari et al., 2018**).

MDR-TB cases showed a strong association with second-line drug use (OR: 2.71), aligning with global evidence that resistance to first-line therapies necessitates advanced regimens. Lower odds for rifampicin resistance, mono-resistance, and poly-drug resistance suggest under-detection or incomplete evaluation in these subsets. The limited prevalence of XDR-TB in the cohort further restricted its statistical significance.

In this study, the mean adherence score was 7.1 ± 1.4 , suggesting a moderate overall level of compliance. However, the presence of nearly one-fifth of patients with poor adherence is concerning, as inadequate treatment adherence remains one of the major contributors to treatment failure, relapse, and the emergence of drug-resistant TB strains. These findings align with results from studies in Ethiopia (**Lemma Tirore, L., et al., 2024**), and China (**Zhu, Q, et al., 2022**) indicating a persistent global challenge in maintaining consistent medication use among TB patients.

Factors contributing to poor adherence identified in this study were, low educational attainment, HIV co-infection, and MDR-TB diagnosis. These findings are consistent with evidence from a meta-analysis by **Du, L., et al. (2020)**, which reported that social and structural barriers, including poverty, stigma, and health system inefficiencies, significantly affect adherence rates. The moderate overall adherence and the observed disparities between patient groups highlight

the importance of strengthening adherence-focused interventions. Incorporating community-based directly observed therapy (DOT), digital adherence technologies (such as SMS reminders and electronic medication monitors), and psychosocial counseling could enhance adherence, particularly among recurrent TB and HIV co-infected patients. In addition, health education programs targeting low-literacy populations and expanding outreach services in remote areas may help close the adherence gap (Sazali, M. F., et al, 2023).

This study has several limitations. First, its cross-sectional design precludes establishing causal relationships between the variables assessed. Second, the study was conducted at selected DOTS centers in Tamil Nadu, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions or settings. Third, adherence was evaluated using self-reported measures, which are subject to recall and social desirability biases. Fourth, the exclusion of severely ill, mentally ill, and pregnant or lactating patients may have led to selection bias. Additionally, the sample size, though adequate for primary analyses, may not be sufficient to explore less common predictors or outcomes. Finally, incomplete or missing data from patient records could have impacted the accuracy of resistance and treatment pattern assessments. Future research with larger, more diverse populations and longitudinal designs is needed to validate and expand upon these findings.

CONCLUSIONS

Drug resistance among tuberculosis patients in India presents a significant public health challenge, with the increasing rate among new patients signaling a troubling rise in primary resistance. This trend threatens ongoing TB control efforts, particularly as previously treated individuals, those presumed to have MDR-TB, urban populations, hospital-based patients, and residents of certain states such as Tamil Nadu experience higher rates of resistance. To enhance the effectiveness of TB control strategies, it is crucial to implement targeted interventions and provide tailored counseling. Ensuring optimal medication adherence must remain a central focus. National TB programs should prioritize addressing both personal and systemic obstacles to care to reduce relapse rates, curb drug resistance, and advance progress toward eliminating tuberculosis as a public health threat.

References:

Bagcchi, S. (2023). WHO's Global Tuberculosis Report 2022. *The Lancet Microbe*, 4(1), e20. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247\(22\)00302-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247(22)00302-3).

- Bai, W., & Ameyaw, E. K. (2024). Global, regional and national trends in tuberculosis incidence and main risk factors: A study using data from 2000 to 2021. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-17209-1>.
- Bhargava, A., Chatterjee, M., Jain, Y., Chatterjee, B., Kataria, A., Bhargava, M., Kataria, R., D'Souza, R., Jain, R., Benedetti, A., & Pai, M. (2013). Nutritional status of adult patients with pulmonary tuberculosis in rural central India and its association with mortality. *PLOS ONE*, 8(10), e77979. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0077979>.
- Chadha, V. K., Praseeja, P., Srivastava, R., Shivashankar, B. A., Kumar, N. H., Padmesh, R., Suganthi, P., Umadevi, G., Narayana, L., Magesh, V., & Nagendra, N. (2022). Pre-treatment delay and out-of-pocket expenses by notified new tuberculosis patients in an Indian megacity. *Indian Journal of Tuberculosis*, 69(4), 446–452. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijtb.2022.05.004>.
- Chakraborty, P., Bajeli, S., Kaushal, D., Radotra, B. D., & Kumar, A. (2021). Biofilm formation in the lung contributes to virulence and drug tolerance of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Nature Communications*, 12(1), 1606. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-21807-9>.
- Chandra, D. K., Moll, A. P., Altice, F. L., Didomizio, E., Andrews, L., & Sheno, S. V. (2022). Structural barriers to implementing recommended tuberculosis preventive treatment in primary care clinics in rural South Africa. *Global Public Health*, 17(4), 555–568. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17441692.2020.1865413>.
- Chauhan, A., Parmar, M., Dash, G. C., Solanki, H., Chauhan, S., Sharma, J., Sahoo, K. C., Mahapatra, P., Rao, R., Kumar, R., & Rade, K. (2023). The prevalence of tuberculosis infection in India: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 157(2–3), 135–151. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijmr.IJMR_2451_21.
- Desikan, P., Panwalkar, N., Chaudhuri, S., Khan, Z., Punde, R. P., Pauranik, A., Mirza, S. B., Ranjan, R., Anand, S., & Sachdeva, K. S. (2020). Burden of baseline resistance of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* to fluoroquinolones and second-line injectables in central India. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 114(4), 249–254. <https://doi.org/10.1093/trstmh/traa008>.
- Du, L., Chen, X., Zhu, X., Zhang, Y., Wu, R., Xu, J., Ji, H., Zhou, L., & Lu, X. (2020). Determinants of Medication Adherence for Pulmonary Tuberculosis Patients During

- Continuation Phase in Dalian, Northeast China. *Patient preference and adherence*, 14, 1119–1128. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PPA.S243734>.
- Gopalan, N., Srinivasalu, V. A., Chinnayan, P., Velayutham, B., Bhaskar, A., Santhanakrishnan, R., Senguttuvan, T., Rathinam, S., Ayyamperumal, M., Satagopan, K., & Rajendran, D. (2021). Predictors of unfavorable responses to therapy in rifampicin-sensitive pulmonary tuberculosis using an integrated approach of radiological presentation and sputum mycobacterial burden. *PLOS ONE*, 16(9), e0257647. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0257647>.
- Jain, M., Rajpal, S., Arora, V. K., Bhargav, S., & Chopra, K. K. (2021). White paper on challenges and opportunities for TB elimination with focus on COVID & Post-COVID era. *Indian Journal of Tuberculosis*, 68(1), 134–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijtb.2020.12.005>.
- Kant, S., & Tyagi, R. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 on tuberculosis: Challenges and opportunities. *Therapeutic Advances in Infectious Disease*, 8, 20499361211016973. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20499361211016973>.
- Lemma Tirore, L., Ersido, T., Beyene Handiso, T., & Shiferaw Areba, A. (2024). Non-adherence to anti-tuberculosis treatment and associated factors among TB patients in public health facilities of Hossana town, Southern Ethiopia, 2022. *Frontiers in medicine*, 11, 1360351. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2024.1360351>.
- Meghji, J., Gregorius, S., Madan, J., Chitimbe, F., Thomson, R., Rylance, J., Banda, N. P., Gordon, S. B., Corbett, E. L., Mortimer, K., & Squire, S. B. (2021). The long-term effect of pulmonary tuberculosis on income and employment in a low-income, urban setting. *Thorax*, 76(4), 387–395. <https://doi.org/10.1136/thoraxjnl-2020-215338>.
- Merchant, S. A., Shaikh, M. J., & Nadkarni, P. (2022). Tuberculosis conundrum—Current and future scenarios: A proposed comprehensive approach combining laboratory, imaging, and computing advances. *World Journal of Radiology*, 14(6), 114–123. <https://doi.org/10.4329/wjr.v14.i6.114>.
- Nair, D., Navneethapandian, P. D., Tripathy, J. P., Harries, A. D., Klinton, J. S., Watson, B., Sivaramakrishnan, G. N., Reddy, D. S., Murali, L., Natrajan, M., & Swaminathan, S. (2016). Impact of rapid molecular diagnostic tests on time to treatment initiation and outcomes in patients with multidrug-resistant tuberculosis, Tamil Nadu, India.

- Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 110(9), 534–541.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/trstmh/trw061>.
- Sazali, M. F., Rahim, S. S. S. A., Mohammad, A. H., Kadir, F., Payus, A. O., Avoi, R., Jeffree, M. S., Omar, A., Ibrahim, M. Y., Atil, A., Tuah, N. M., Dapari, R., Lansing, M. G., Rahim, A. A. A., & Azhar, Z. I. (2023). Improving Tuberculosis Medication Adherence: The Potential of Integrating Digital Technology and Health Belief Model. *Tuberculosis and respiratory diseases*, 86(2), 82–93. <https://doi.org/10.4046/trd.2022.0148>.
- Sharma, J. B., Sharma, E., Sharma, S., & Dharmendra, S. (2018). Female genital tuberculosis: Revisited. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 148(Suppl 1), S71–S83. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijmr.IJMR_697_18.
- Silva, S., Arinaminpathy, N., Atun, R., Goosby, E., & Reid, M. (2021). Economic impact of tuberculosis mortality in 120 countries and the cost of not achieving the Sustainable Development Goals tuberculosis targets: A full-income analysis. *The Lancet Global Health*, 9(10), e1372–e1379. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(21\)00367-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(21)00367-0).
- Vishwakarma, D., Gaidhane, A., Sahu, S., & Rathod, A. S. (2023). Multi-drug resistance tuberculosis (MDR-TB) challenges in India: A review. *Cureus*, 15(12), e49789. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.49789>.
- World Health Organization. (2022, October 10). *WHO Global Task Force on TB Impact Measurement: Report of a subgroup meeting on methods used by WHO to estimate TB disease burden (11–12 May 2022, Geneva, Switzerland)*. World Health Organization. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/363262>.
- World Health Organization. (2023, July 25). *Use of targeted next-generation sequencing to detect drug-resistant tuberculosis: Rapid communication*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240071872>.
- Zhu, Q. Q., Wang, J., Sam, N. B., Luo, J., Liu, J., & Pan, H. F. (2022). Factors Associated with Non-Adherence for Prescribed Treatment in 201 Patients with Multidrug-Resistant and Rifampicin-Resistant Tuberculosis in Anhui Province, China. *Medical science monitor : international medical journal of experimental and clinical research*, 28, e935334. <https://doi.org/10.12659/MSM.935334>.

TABLES

Table 1: Socio-demographic and behavioral characteristics of tuberculosis patients (N=215)

Variable	No. of patients N=215	Percentage (%)	p-value
Gender			
Male	151	70.3	0.03
Female	64	29.7	
Age			
<18	10	4.6	0.05
18-30	34	15.6	
31-40	47	21.8	
41-50	64	29.6	
51-60	37	17.1	
>60	24	11	
Residence			
Urban	77	36	0.01
Rural	138	64	
Socioeconomic status			
Lower class	138	64	0.12
Middle class	60	28.1	
Upper class	17	7.8	
Education			
Low education (≤primary)	86	40	0.001
Secondary	70	32.5	
Tertiary	59	27.4	
Personal History			
Smoking			
Yes	154	71.8	0.02
No	61	28.1	
Alcoholism			
Yes	124	57.8	0.09
No	91	42.1	
Use of illicit drugs			
Yes	27	12.5	0.15
No	188	87.5	

Table 2 Clinical characterization and treatment patterns among TB patients

Characteristics	No. of patients N=215	Percentage (%)	p-value
Types of TB			
New TB case	64	29.6	0.03
Recurrent TB case	77	36	
Treatment after failure	34	15.6	
Treatment after loss to follow-up	30	14	
Other previously treated patients	10	4.6	
Site of TB			
Pulmonary	168	78.1	0.01
Extrapulmonary	47	21.8	
Type of TB strain Identified			
Susceptible	74	34.3	0.05
Rifampicin resistant (RR)	17	7.8	
Mono-resistance (MR)	17	7.8	
Poly-Drug Resistance (PDR)	10	4.6	
Multidrug-resistant TB (MDR)	94	43.7	
Extensively drug-resistant TB (XRD)	3	1.5	
Family history of TB			
Yes	54	25	0.08
No	161	75	
Known HIV/AIDS patient			
Yes	74	34.3	0.01
No	141	65.6	
Comorbidities			

Yes	64	29.6	0.09
No	151	70.3	
Previously treated with first-line drugs	104	48.4	0.02
Previously treated with second-line drugs	24	11	
Undergone surgery related to TB	40	18.8	0.15

Table 3 Factors associated with prescribing second-line TB drugs in the treatment of new and retreatment TB cases.

Character	Total	Use of 2 nd -line TB drugs		Univariate analysis		
		N=215		%	OD	95% CI Low
Sex						
Male	151	83	54.6	2.1	0.28	3.2
Female	64	10	15.6	ref		
Age groups (years)						
<18	10	0	4.6	ref		
18-30	34	5	14	1.29	0.63	2.03
31-40	47	9	18.7	1.81	1.20	3.0
41-50	64	16	25	2.15	1.23	3.6
51-60	37	5	14	3.1	1.96	4.6
>60	24	2	7.8	0.31	0.02	1.3
Types of TB						
New TB case	64	3	4.6	ref		
Retreatment	77	46	59.3	3.1	1.62	4.21
Site of TB						
Pulmonary	168	81	48.4	ref		
Extrapulmonary	47	10	21.8	1.6	0.5	2.41
Type of TB strain Identified						
Susceptible	74	10	14	ref		
Rifampicin resistant (RR)	17	1	7.8	0.9	0.03	1.61
Mono-resistance (MR)	17	1	7.8	0.3	0.06	1.32
Poly-Drug Resistance (PDR)	10	1	4.6	1.5	0.61	2.1

Multidrug-resistant TB (MRD)	94	40	43.75	2.71	1.62	3.89
Extensively drug-resistant TB (XRD)	3	0	1.5	0.34	0.06	1.23

Table 4: Level of medication adherence (based on MMAS-8 scale) (n = 141*)

Adherence level	Score range	New TB cases n=64	Recurrent TB cases n=77	p-value
High adherence	8	39 (60.9%)	28 (36.4%)	
Medium adherence	6-7	18 (28.1%)	26 (33.8%)	
Low adherence	<6	7 (10.9%)	23 (29.8%)	
Mean adherence score (\pm SD)	-	7.1 \pm 1.4	6.2 \pm 3.2	0.003
Overall association (Chi-square)				0.002

*Subset analysis excluding MDR-TB cases for comparability.

Table 5. Factors associated with medication non-adherence (binary logistic regression)

Variable	Category	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p-value
Age \geq 45 years	Yes vs. No	1.48 (0.83–2.62)	0.183
Male gender	Yes vs. No	1.25 (0.72-2.19)	0.432
Low education (\leq primary)	Yes vs. No	2.11 (1.09-4.07)	0.027
MDR-TB diagnosis	Yes vs. No	2.54 (1.33-4.82)	0.005
HIV co-infection	Yes vs. No	3.06 (1.11-8.44)	0.034

FIGURES

Figure 1: Clinical characterization of Tubercular patients

Figure 2: Type of strains identified in TB patients

Note: H, isoniazid; R, rifampicin; Z, pyrazinamide; E, ethambutol; S, streptomycin.

Figure 3 Anti-tubercular regimens used in the treatment of new and retreatment TB cases

Figure 4 Proportion of TB patients treated with each type of anti-tuberculosis drug